

Wachendorfia multiflora Kleinrooikanol or Brown butterfly lily

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Group: Monocot

Size: The smallest species in this genus, typically growing up to 25–30 cm high.

Distribution:

Western Cape, South Africa.

Importance:

Wachendorfia multiflora has asymmetrical flowers, with styles deflected either to the right or left, resulting in roughly equal numbers of right- and left-morph plants. A genome assembly of the sister species, *Wachendorfia paniculata*, has identified a hemizygous region present only in right-morph plants. A high-quality assembly of the *W. multiflora* genome will enable comparative genomics to investigate the evolution of this supergene locus.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 93.6 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 11.32 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye

Genome Length: 0.34 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 82.4%, Duplicated: 17.4%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 1 521.96 kilobases

Contig number: 3 001

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